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Leukotriene activation is a major property of NOD2 mutation in human monocytes.

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Ltb4r, ltb4r2 and lt4cs were all activated by NOD2 mutant monocytes from patients with Crohn's Disease in the absence of stimulus.

Citations

1. Sharon, P. and Stenson, W.F., 1984. Enhanced synthesis of leukotriene B4 by colonic mucosa in inflammatory bowel disease. Gastroenterology, 86(3), pp.453-460.